

From X-rays to Algorithms Leading to Smart Aligned Smile: AI in Modern Orthodontics

Received on : 20-07-2024 | Accepted on : 24-07-2024 | Published on : 04-09-2024

Dr A Annie Maxwell¹
Dr Divyaroop Rai²
Dr Shantanu Sharma³
Dr Pooja Sharma⁴
Dr Nitin Tripathi⁵

¹P.G. Student
Department of Orthodontics and
Dentofacial Orthopaedics,
NIMS Dental College & Hospital,
Jaipur, Rajasthan, India.

²Professor and Head,
Department of Orthodontics and
Dentofacial Orthopaedics,
NIMS Dental College & Hospital,
Jaipur, Rajasthan, India.

³Associate Professor,
Department of Orthodontics and
Dentofacial Orthopaedics,
NIMS Dental College & Hospital
Jaipur, Rajasthan, India.

⁴P.G. Student
Department of Orthodontics and
Dentofacial Orthopaedics,
NIMS Dental College & Hospital,
Jaipur, Rajasthan, India.

⁵P.G. Student
Department of Orthodontics and
Dentofacial Orthopaedics,
NIMS Dental College & Hospital,
Jaipur, Rajasthan, India.

Corresponding Author

Dr. A. Annie Maxwell
P. G. Student,
Department of Orthodontics and
Dentofacial Orthopaedics,
NIMS Dental College & Hospital, Jaipur,
Rajasthan, India.

Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) is revolutionizing the field of orthodontics, which helps to understand diagnosis and treatment plan of the cases with the help of bulk prior data and enhances the clinical outcomes. AI algorithms and machine learning techniques enables precise diagnosis and personalized treatment plans by analyzing large amounts of patient data, including radiographs, photographs, and 3D scans. AI-powered tools assist orthodontists in evaluating whether extraction or non extraction protocol has to be used , helps to predict tooth movement priorly, optimize aligner designs, and monitor treatment progress in real time.

These advancements haslead to reducing chair time and improving patient satisfaction. As AI technology continues to evolve, it holds the promise of further transforming orthodontics through improved accuracy, efficiency, and accessibility, ultimately benefiting both practitioners and patients.

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI), a term first introduced in 1955 by John McCarthy, describes the ability of machines to perform tasks that are classified as intelligent.¹

It was a 2-month workshop: Dartmouth Summer Research Project on Artificial Intelligence led by John McCarthy, Marvin Minsky, Nathaniel Rochester, and Claude Shannon and this concept was only on paper. But in 1957- 1975 due to the accessibility and the advances in the computer technology AI field grew faster with different kinds of algorithms for different software.²

Artificial intelligence is basically a machine that copies the cognitive functions of human intelligence and helps to take off the manual load of an individual.

Google-developed AI application called AlphaGo in the year 2015 was the breakthrough. With the introduction of Chat GPT in the year 2022 , AI development for different fields bloomed including in the field of medicine and dentistry.³

In the field of diagnostic imaging, AI can be categorized into 1) operational AI,

which increases healthcare delivery.

- 2) diagnostic AI, which aids in the interpretation of clinical images;
- 3) predictive AI, which forecasts future outcomes.⁴The main goal of AI in diagnostic imaging is to detect and cut each structure and classify them into pathologies.⁵ AI tools can analyse images obtained from various imaging modalities, ranging from X-ray to MRI.

Computer-based diagnostics have gained momentum in the field of health care due to the Convolutional neural network advantage which helps in distinguishing images that detect lesions not seen by the human eye.

CNNs have been successfully used in image-based diagnosis in which the segmentation of the brain tumor and the detection of lung lesions are carried out automatically.⁶

Types of AI

How to Cite This Article: Maxwell et al.: From X-rays to Algorithms Leading to Smart Aligned Smile: AI in Modern Orthodontics...AJOAD.2024

- 1) Weak AI - uses a program trained to solve single or specific tasks.
- 2) Strong AI- Strong AI refers to the ability and intelligence of AI equalling that of humans it has its own awareness and behaviour as flexible as human.⁷

There are further categorised in :

- A) Symbolic AI: easily understandable to human⁸
- B) Machine learning AI: Coined by Arthur Samuel in 1952. It relies on models.

Based on the learning strategy and intended result, machine learning techniques can be divided into three categories. Supervised learning is the first kind and is applied to problems involving prediction or classification in which the result is known ahead of time. Here, the algorithm gains knowledge from a labelled dataset and applies it to provide precise predictions about unknown data. Unsupervised learning, the second kind, looks for hidden structures and patterns in data without knowing the outcome in advance. This kind of learning is helpful for tasks like anomaly identification and clustering.

Last but not least, reinforcement learning uses a machine to create an algorithm that optimizes a predetermined reward by using data from earlier iterations of the machine. This kind of education.⁹ It Consists of Deep learning , ANN and CNN.

A subset of machine learning called deep learning (DL) includes machines autonomously calculating particular attributes of an input. Artificial neural networks (ANNs), created in the 1990s, provide the foundation for DL.

- A) CNN is a deep learning model mostly utilized for picture production and recognition. Convolution layers in a CNN are utilized to create feature maps from input data by applying convolution kernels.¹⁰
- B) ANN- It has 3 layers – Input layer , hidden layer and output layer .

Why AI is Important?

Healthcare workers can utilize AI to analyze future situations by using its ability to learn from past data and make conclusions from cases.

Dental Diagnosis

Orthodontic diagnosis is a challenging task since it requires a thorough simultaneous assessment of different facial components from different perspectives.

Digital dentistry tools enable the collection of patient data on a digital platform, transforming it into a database that can be used for diagnosis and treatment.

The utilization of artificial intelligence and machine learning technologies has resulted in a notable decrease in the assessment workload and the prevention of diagnostic variants.¹²

A) Radiographs: Cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) and orthopantomograms (OPGs) are two radiological techniques that are essential for orthodontic diagnosis, treatment planning, and follow-up.¹³ A complete tool is required to assist in the radiological diagnosis procedure. Multimodular AI-based diagnostic systems have arisen in answer to this need.

Using CNNs, Diagnocat Ltd. (San Francisco, CA, USA)

offers accurate and thorough dental diagnoses. The technology allows for volumetric assessment, identification of oral pathology (including periapical lesions and caries), and segmentation and enumeration of teeth.

In an oral CBCT examination, the overall diagnostic performance of two groups one with AI assistance and the other without was evaluated in a recent study by Ezhov et al 2021)¹⁴. The findings demonstrated that the AI system greatly enhanced dentists' diagnostic abilities, resulting in increased sensitivity.

Rahimi et al¹⁵, 48 studies were examined to assess the classification models' accuracy in detecting caries. Depending on the imaging modalities, the reported diagnosis accuracy ranged from 68% to 99.2%. According to the study's findings, deep learning models could facilitate clinical processes and show potential for caries diagnosis.

Cephalometric Analysis: It is a crucial diagnostic tool that supports assessment of the incisor placement, molar relationship, profile, etc. These days, manual tracing is a rather laborious task, thus for simple evaluation With the introduction of automated cephalometric analysis, only manual landmark identification is required , the x-ray may now be traced and the analysis can be finished by itself.

According to Nishimoto in the year 2019 concluded a study Using cephalogram photos from the internet is a workable method for landmark prediction, despite the wide range of image quality.

Hwang et al. (2020)¹⁷ concluded that automated cephalometric landmark identification can be as reliable as an experienced human reader. Similarly, Kim et al. [65] achieved landmark definition accuracies between 88% and 92% using AI. These authors also found that, compared with manual methods, AI methods demonstrated.

Automated cephalometric landmark detection can be just as dependable as a skilled human reader, according to Hwang et al. (2020)¹⁷. Similar to this, Kim et al.¹⁸ used AI to attain groundbreaking definition accuracy of 88% to 92%. Additionally, these authors discovered that when compared to manual techniques, AI algorithms showed.

Yu et al.¹⁹ did not find any statistically significant differences between the automated cephalometric analysis findings and the results derived from manually recognized landmarks in their other research.

A study by Serafin et al.²⁰ published in year 2023 revealed a mean difference of 2.44 mm between manual and three-dimensional (3D) automated land marking.

Blum et al²¹ The precision of automatic landmark detection is comparable to that of manual landmark identification, and it takes less time. The achieved accuracy of the system was in range of clinically acceptance.

Ueda et al.²²The anteroposterior maxillofacial morphology and vertical dimension used by the AI model developed in this study allowed for an appropriate classification of patients into one of the nine combined face classes. This can guarantee accuracy independent of the number of years a practitioner has worked in a clinical setting, improving the standardi-

zation of maxillofacial morphology classification.

All these studies concluded that the greater accuracy in landmark identification has increased due to the introduction of AI which lead to a reduction in the time and human labour required.

B) Determination of Skeletal Age: Growth and maturation plays the most important role in orthodontics as all the treatment plan relies over the growth and maturation of the jaws, teeth and cranial base.

Nevertheless, individual differences in development dynamics during adolescence make it inadequate to estimate further growth based only on chronological age.²³

A better metric for assessing individual growth is skeletal age, which can be determined by wrist X-rays or cervical vertebral maturation (CVM). In conventional diagnostic orthodontic procedures, wrist X-rays are not recommended; however, lateral cephalometric X-rays can be used to evaluate the CVM.²⁴

C) TMJ Evaluation: Temporomandibular joint osteoarthritis (TMJOA) is a specific type of temporomandibular disorder that can result in significant joint pain, dysfunction, dental malocclusion, and a decreased overall quality of life.²⁵ The assessment of TMJ function and morphology is essential in orthodontic and dental treatments. Radiographic examination, such as OPG/CBCT, confirms the presence of TMJOA by revealing bony changes, while MRI is the preferred modality for evaluating joint discs.

Marcelo Kreiner²⁶ did a study in the year 2022 that aimed to develop and test the performance of a novel neural network (multilayer perceptron) with diagnostic capabilities in orofacial pain and TMD, including some types of referred pain. Result- This study showed, for the first time, that an artificial neural network can help medical and general dental clinicians diagnose several types of orofacial pain and dysfunction, including TMD, neuropathic, neurovascular, and a referred cardiac pain. In some cases, the MLP appears to have a life-saving role.

In order to assess the automated diagnosis of disc perforation, internal derangement, TMJ osteoarthritis, and masticatory muscle anomalies, Jha et al.²⁷ performed a more comprehensive study of 17 publications. According to the meta-analysis, the assessed AI models had excellent diagnostic performance; their specificity and accuracy ranged from 73% to 100% and 84% to 99.9%, respectively.

D) Extraction Decision Making: The most demanding issue that an orthodontist faces while making a treatment plan is whether to proceed with the non-extraction protocol or an extraction protocol.

An artificial neural network was used by Kong et al. The results showed that the network could predict extraction and non-extraction with 94% accuracy, extraction patterns with 4.2% accuracy, and anchoring patterns with 92.8% accuracy. The study concludes that less experienced orthodontists can be guided throughout treatment by using the neural network.²⁹

To decide whether extraction is required for malocclusion patients between the ages of 11 and 15, Xie developed a de-

cision-making expert system (ES).

According to the study, Jung used the ANN to forecast the precise extraction patterns, correctly determining with an accuracy of 84% whether extraction or non-extraction was required.²⁹

Similar results were achieved by Li et al. (2019)³⁰, who reported a 94% accuracy for extraction versus nonextraction predictions, 84.2% for extraction patterns, and 92.8% for anchorage patterns. These studies identified several features that are important in predicting treatment efficacy, such as crowding of the upper arch, position of anterior teeth, lower incisor inclination, overjet, overbite, and capability for lip closure.

E) Orthognathic Surgery Decision Making and Planning: Whether to plan for a orthognathic surgery in cases of borderline cases or to camouflage is a questionable topic.

Soft tissue profiles were assessed by Jeong et al.³¹ using facial picture data. 89% of the assessed CNN's surgical case classifications were accurate.

A model developed by Choi et al.³² achieved an accuracy range of 88% to 97% in predicting the necessity for surgery and providing an extraction plan for surgical patients.

F) Treatment Outcome Prediction: Orthodontists face the challenge of selecting the most appropriate treatment strategy for each patient based on their expectations, socioeconomic conditions, cultural background, and skills. However, procedures such as extractions and orthognathic surgeries are irreversible and can result in permanent patient dissatisfaction. Therefore, accurately predicting treatment outcomes is crucial for both practitioners and patients. Fortunately, a growing body of literature demonstrates the effectiveness of AI in predicting orthodontic and orthognathic treatment outcome.

In terms of six dimensions of tooth movement, Woo et al.³³ compared the accuracy of three different automated digital setup programs with a manual setup.

The outcomes showed that while the automated virtual setup software components were generally effective, more manual changes would still be necessary in clinical practice.

Using modified C-palatal plates, Park et al.³⁴ utilized a CNN model to predict the cephalometric changes of Class II patients, and they got an overall accuracy of 1.79 ± 1.77 mm.

In order to anticipate the 3D changes in facial morphology following orthodontic (including the extraction of four premolars) or orthognathic surgical treatment, Tanikawa et al.³⁵ integrated geometric morphometric approaches with deep learning. In the surgical and orthodontic groups, the average inaccuracy of the suggested system was 0.94 ± 0.43 mm and 0.69 ± 0.28 mm, respectively.

To predict patients' experiences with Invisalign treatment, Xu et al.³⁶ used an ANN model using training data consisting of 17 clinical characteristics.

High prediction accuracy of 87.7% for pain, 93.4% for anxiety, and 92.4% for quality of life was attained by the suggested model.

G) Modeling: The AI model demonstrated a modest degree of accuracy in predicting results, which is consistent with other

studies that have demonstrated the usefulness of AI in medical prediction tasks. With a success rate of almost 73%, it is possible that a sizable percentage of patients had treatment outcomes that aligned with the AI model's predictions.³⁷

H) Treatment Optimization:

A) Aligner Therapy: Thurzo et al.³⁸ The goal is to assess the effects of using computerized tailored decision algorithms as an upgrade to an already-existing clinical orthodontic application (app) in response to observed and predicted patient behavior. They concluded that by implementing application updates that incorporate computerized decision processes, current healthcare applications can perform much better clinically and increase patient compliance. A secondary finding is that, by telemedicine concepts, dental monitoring is a helpful tool for assessing clinical situations.

B) Bracket Placement: Features of SureSmile technology includes:

1. OraScanner
2. Wire bending robot
3. Digital bracket placement³⁹

An innovative use that improves the accuracy and effectiveness of orthodontic treatments is AI-driven bracket placement. Here's how bracket placement is being revolutionized by AI:

- i) Imaging and Scanning Digitally 3D Imaging produces a comprehensive digital model which has high precision.
- ii) Planning and Analysis Optimal Positioning: To ascertain the best location for every bracket, artificial intelligence algorithms examine the digital model. This entails determining the ideal migration route for the tooth as well as its current and intended final positions.
Customization: Taking into account individual variances in tooth alignment and shape, the system adjusts the bracket placement for every tooth.
- iii) Virtual Setup Simulation: AI models the teeth virtually, simulating the full course of treatment from beginning to end.
- iv) Guided Placement: The orthodontist is assisted in precisely positioning the brackets on the teeth by the AI-generated bespoke placement jigs or templates.
Decreased Errors: By guaranteeing that brackets are positioned precisely in accordance with the digital plan, these guides lower human mistake and enhance the effectiveness of therapy.
- v) Real-Time Modifications Instant Feedback: During the bracket insertion process, artificial intelligence (AI) technologies offer real-time feedback, assisting orthodontists in making quick adjustments as needed.
Enhanced Accuracy: By utilizing a feedback loop, any deviations from the ideal positioning are promptly detected and fixed.
- vi) Predictive Result Predictive analytics: AI makes predictions about how teeth will move throughout treatment using predictive analytics. This aids in foreseeing possible problems and making proactive corrections.
Better Outcomes: AI helps produce more predictable and

gratifying outcomes for patients by forecasting outcomes.³⁹

Conclusion

The field of orthodontics is changing because to artificial intelligence (AI), which is providing patient care with previously unheard-of levels of precision, efficiency, and personalization. The accuracy of orthodontic procedures has increased thanks to AI's skills in diagnosis, treatment planning, and monitoring. This has reduced treatment times and improved results. Artificial Intelligence (AI) enhances patient treatments by optimizing procedures like bracket insertion and aligner design through the use of sophisticated imaging, predictive modeling, and real-time feedback.

AI also makes teleorthodontics and remote consultations easier, increasing accessibility to high-quality orthodontic treatment. The application of AI technology in orthodontics promises even more breakthroughs as it develops, including improved patient happiness, increased treatment accuracy, and more accessibility to care. In the end, artificial intelligence (AI) will play a major role in the development of orthodontics and usher in a new era of creativity and quality in dental care.

References

1. McCarthy, J.; Minsky, M.L.; Rochester, N.; Shannon, C.E. A Proposal for the Dartmouth Summer Research Project on Artificial Intelligence. *AI Mag.* 2006, 27, 12
2. Buchanan BG. A (very) brief history of artificial intelligence. *Ai Magazine.* 2005 Dec 15;26(4):53
3. Haenlein, M.; Kaplan, A. A Brief History of Artificial Intelligence: On the Past, Present, and Future of Artificial Intelligence. *Calif. Manag. Rev.* 2019, 61, 5–14
4. Pianykh, O.S.; Langs, G.; Dewey, M.; Enzmann, D.R.; Herold, C.J.; Schoenberg, S.O.; Brink, J.A. Continuous Learning AI in Radiology: Implementation Principles and Early Applications. *Radiology* 2020, 297, 6–14.
5. Milam, M.E.; Koo, C.W. The Current Status and Future of FDA-Approved Artificial Intelligence Tools in Chest Radiology in the United States. *Clin. Radiol.* 2023, 78, 115–122
6. Etemad L, Wu T-H, Heiner P, et al. Machine learning from clinical data sets of a contemporary decision for orthodontic tooth extraction. *OrthodCraniofac Res.* 2021;24(Suppl. 2):193–200.
7. (Ding H, Wu J, Zhao W, Matinlinna JP, Burrow MF, Tsoi JK. Artificial intelligence in dentistry A review. *Frontiers in Dental Medicine.* 2023 Feb 20; 4:1085251)
8. Haugeland J. *Artificial intelligence: The very idea.* MIT press; 1989 Jan 6.
9. Bishop, C. *Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning*; Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 2007; Volume 16
- 10) Ding H, Wu J, Zhao W, Matinlinna JP, Burrow MF, Tsoi JK. Artificial intelligence in dentistry A review. *Frontiers in Dental Medicine.* 2023 Feb 20; 4:1085251
11. Bichu YM, Hansa I, Bichu AY, Premjani P, Flores-Mir C, Vaid NR. Applications of artificial intelligence and machine learning in orthodontics: a scoping review. *Progress in orthodontics.* 2021 Dec;22(1):1-1
12. Ahmed N, Chethana AY, Aymen U, Rahul NA. Artificial intelligence in orthodontics: A way towards modernization. *technology.* 2023;7:8
13. De Grauwe A, Ayaz I, Shujaat S, Dimitrov S, Gbadegbegnon L, VandeVannet B, Jacobs R. CBCT in orthodontics: a systematic review on justification of CBCT in a paediatric population prior to orthodontic treatment. *European journal of orthodontics.* 2019 Aug 8;41(4):381-9.
14. Ezhov, M.; Gusarev, M.; Golitsyna, M.; Yates, J.M.; Kushnerev, E.; Tamimi, D.; Aksoy, S.; Shumilov, E.; Sanders, A.; Orhan, K. Clinically Applicable Artificial Intelligence System for Dental Diagnosis with CBCT. *Sci. Rep.* 2021, 11, 15006.

15. Mohammad-Rahimi, H.; Motamedian, S.R.; Rohban, M.H.; Krois, J.; Uribe, S.E.; Mahmoudinia, E.; Rokhsad, R.; Nadimi, M.; Schwendicke, F. Deep Learning for Caries Detection: A Systematic Review. *J. Dent.* 2022, 122, 104115
16. Nishimoto S., Sotsuka Y., Kawai K., Ishise H., Kakibuchi M. Personal Computer-Based Cephalometric Landmark Detection With Deep Learning, Using Cephalograms on the Internet. *J. Craniofacial Surg.* 2019; 30: 91–95. doi: 10.1097/SCS.0000000000004901.
17. Hwang, H.W.; Park, J.H.; Moon, J.H.; Yu, Y.; Kim, H.; Her, S.B.; Srinivasan, G.; Aljanabi, M.N.A.; Donatelli, R.E.; Lee, S.J. Automated Identification of Cephalometric Landmarks: Part 2-Might It Be Better than Human? *Angle Orthod.* 2020, 90, 69–76
18. Kim, H.; Shim, E.; Park, J.; Kim, Y.J.; Lee, U.; Kim, Y. Web-Based Fully Automated Cephalometric Analysis by Deep Learning. *Comput. Methods Programs Biomed.* 2020, 194, 105513.
19. Yu, H.J.; Cho, S.R.; Kim, M.J.; Kim, W.H.; Kim, J.W.; Choi, J. Automated Skeletal Classification with Lateral Cephalometry Based on Artificial Intelligence. *J. Dent. Res.* 2020, 99, 249–256.
20. Serafin, M.; Baldini, B.; Cabitza, F.; Carrafiello, G.; Baselli, G.; Del Fabbro, M.; Sforza, C.; Caprioglio, A.; Tartaglia, G.M. Accuracy of Automated 3D Cephalometric Landmarks by Deep Learning Algorithms: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Radiol. Medica* 2023, 128, 544–555
21. Blum F.M.S., Möhlhenrich S.C., Raith S., Pankert T., Peters F., Wolf M., Hölzle F., Modabber A. Evaluation of an artificial intelligence-based algorithm for automated localization of craniofacial landmarks. *Clin. Oral Investig.* 2023;27:2255–2265. doi: 10.1007/s00784-023-04978-4
22. Ueda A., Tussie C., Kim S., Kuwajima Y., Matsumoto S., Kim G., Satoh K., Nagai S. Classification of Maxillofacial Morphology by Artificial Intelligence Using Cephalometric Analysis Measurements. *Diagnostics.* 2023;13:2134.
23. Khanagar, S.B.; Al-Ehaideb, A.; Vishwanathaiah, S.; Maganur, P.C.; Patil, S.; Naik, S.; Baeshen, H.A.; Sarode, S.S. Scope and Performance of Artificial Intelligence Technology in Orthodontic Diagnosis, Treatment Planning, and Clinical Decision-Making A Systematic Review. *J. Dent. Sci.* 2021, 16, 482–492
24. Szemraj, A.; Wojtaszek-Słomińska, A.; Racka-Pilszak, B. Is the Cervical Vertebral Maturation (CVM) Method Effective Enough to Replace the Hand-Wrist Maturation (HWM) Method in Determining Skeletal Maturation? A Systematic Review. *Eur. J. Radiol.* 2018, 102, 125–128
25. Wang, X.D.; Zhang, J.N.; Gan, Y.H.; Zhou, Y.H. Current Understanding of Pathogenesis and Treatment of TMJ Osteoarthritis. *J. Dent. Res.* 2015, 94, 666–673
26. Kreiner M, Vilorio J. A novel artificial neural network for the diagnosis of orofacial pain and temporomandibular disorders. *Journal of Oral Rehabilitation.* 2022 Sep;49(9):884-9.
27. Jha, N.; Lee, K.S.; Kim, Y.J. Diagnosis of Temporomandibular Disorders Using Artificial Intelligence Technologies: A Systematic Review and Meta Analysis. *PLoS ONE* 2022, 17, e0272715
28. Li P, Kong D, Tang T. Orthodontic treatment planning based on artificial neural networks. *Scientific Rep.* 2019;9(1):1–9.
29. Jung SK, Kim TW. New approach for the diagnosis of extractions with neural network machine learning. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 2016; 149(1):127–33
30. Li, P.; Kong, D.; Tang, T.; Su, D.; Yang, P.; Wang, H.; Zhao, Z.; Liu, Y. Orthodontic Treatment Planning Based on Artificial Neural Networks. *Sci. Rep.* 2019, 9, 2037
31. Jeong, S.H.; Yun, J.P.; Yeom, H.G.; Lim, H.J.; Lee, J.; Kim, B.C. Deep Learning Based Discrimination of Soft Tissue Profiles Requiring Orthognathic Surgery by Facial Photographs. *Sci. Rep.* 2020, 10, 16235.
32. Choi, H.I.; Jung, S.K.; Baek, S.H.; Lim, W.H.; Ahn, S.J.; Yang, I.H.; Kim, T.W. Artificial Intelligent Model with Neural Network Machine Learning for the Diagnosis of Orthognathic Surgery. *J. Craniofacial Surg.* 2019, 30, 1986–1989.
33. Woo H., Jha N., Kim Y.-J., Sung S.-J. Evaluating the accuracy of automated orthodontic digital setup models. *Semin. Orthod.* 2023;29:60–67
34. Park J.H., Kim Y.-J., Kim J., Kim J., Kim I.-H., Kim N., Vaid N.R., Kook Y.-A. Use of artificial intelligence to predict outcomes of nonextraction treatment of Class II malocclusions. *Semin. Orthod.* 2021;27:87–95
35. Tanikawa C., Yamashiro T. Development of novel artificial intelligence systems to predict facial morphology after orthognathic surgery and orthodontic treatment in Japanese patients. *Sci. Rep.* 2021;11:15853
36. Xu L., Mei L., Lu R., Li Y., Li H., Li Y. Predicting patient experience of Invisalign treatment: An analysis using artificial neural network. *Korean J. Orthod.* 2022;52:268–277
37. (Alam MK, Alanazi DS, Alruwaili SR, Alderaan RA. Assessment of AI Models in Predicting Treatment Outcomes in Orthodontics. *Journal of Pharmacy and Bioallied Sciences.* 2024 Feb 1;16(Suppl 1):S540-2.)
38. (Thurzo A, Kurilová V, Varga I. Artificial intelligence in orthodontic smart application for treatment coaching and its impact on clinical performance of patients monitored with AI-TeleHealth system. *InHealthcare* 2021 Dec 7 (Vol. 9, No. 12, p. 1695). MDPI.)
39. Sachdeva RC. SureSmile technology in a patient-centered orthodontic practice. *Journal of Clinical Orthodontics.* 2001 Apr 1;35(4):245-53